

Transcriptome analysis of prostate cancer

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Abstract

Because of the projected rise in the number of prostate cancer cases in 2026, I revised data from the Genomic Data Commons (GDC) Cancer Portal. I performed gene differential expression (DEG) analysis with transcriptome data of acinar cell carcinoma of prostate gland from male patients (tumor $n=197$, control $n=49$). 1314 putative biomarkers ($\log_2FC \geq 1.5$ and $p_{adj} \leq 0.05$) were identified. In addition, I reviewed commercial molecular assays for prostate cancer diagnosis and listed 91 known biomarkers. From these, GRP (ERG $\log_2FC=2.66$, $p_{adj}=1.60e-17$) is the only gene among our putative biomarkers. Finally, I identified as potential biomarkers for therapy 20 genes whose fold change (FC) was ≥ 50 and average TPM of control samples ≤ 10 .

Keywords : prostate cancer, transcriptome, diagnoses, biomarkers

Introduction

Early detection of prostate cancer significantly improves treatment outcomes and survival rates, emphasizing the need for diagnostic biomarkers that can be applied in different cohorts. Several commercial assays already use gene expression to diagnose prostate cancer [1], e.g. Decipher, Oncotype DX (GPS), Prolaris (CCP / CCR), PTEN, ProMark and TMPRSS2-ERG Fusion. In this work, I proposed to

obtain the DEG's from prostate cancer data. Finally, I compared my DEG's with the list of biomarkers already experimentally in use.

Methods

The cohort builder of GDC portal (<https://portal.gdc.cancer.gov/>) accessed on 2026-04-04 was used to obtain data from prostate cancer cases (Experimental Strategy = RNA-Seq, Data Format = tsv, Data Category = transcriptome profiling, Workflow Type = STAR - Counts, Sex at Birth = male, Primary Diagnosis = acinar cell carcinoma, Primary Site = prostate gland). RNA-seq data only were downloaded. Among the 246 samples, 49 and 197 were from normal and tumor tissue type, respectively.

R package DESeq2 [8] was used to obtain differentially expressed genes ($\log_2FC \geq 1.5$ and $padj \leq 0.05$) for samples of Normal versus Tumor tissue types. A github with data and scripts to reproduce the results was made available at : https://github.com/datasciencebioinformatics/BiomarkerIdentification_ProstateCancer/

Table 1 - Biomarker genes for prostate cancer diagnosis assays.

Biomarker	Assay/Type	Genes	Publication
Decipher	Genomic classifier (22-gene RNA)	LASP1, IQGAP3, NFIB, S1PR4, THBS2, ANO7, PCDH7, MYBPC1, EPPK1, TSBP, PBX1, NUSAP1, ZWILCH, UBE2C, CAMK2N1, RABGAP1, PCAT-32, GLYATL1P4/PCAT-80, TNFRSF19	[2]
Oncotype DX (GPS)	RT-PCR score (17 genes: 12 cancer + 5 reference)	ARF1, ATP5E, AZGP1, BGN, CLTC, COL1A1, FAM13C1, FLNC, GPS1, GSN, GSTM2, KLK2, PGK1, SFRP4, SRD5A2, TPM2, TPX2	[3]
Prolaris (CCP / CCR)	Cell-cycle gene panel (31 genes; 16-gene version)	ASPM, CDC2, CDCA8, CDKN3, DTL, FOXM1, KIAA0101, NUSAP1, PRC1, TK1, CLTC, PSMA1, RPL4, RPS29, SLC25A3, UBA52, ASF1B, BIRC5, BUB1B, C18orf24, CDC20, CDCA3, CENPF, CENPM, CEP55, DLGAP5, KIF11, KIF20A, MCM10, ORC6L, PBK, PLK1, PTTG1, RAD51, RAD54L, RRM2, TOP2A, MMADHC, MRFAP1, PPP2CA, PSMC1, RPL8, RPL13A, RPL37, RPL38, TXNL1	[4]
PTEN	Protein/gene loss (IHC, FISH, NGS)	PTEN	[5]
ProMark	Proteomic assay (8-protein panel)	DERL1, CUL2, SMAD4, PDSS2, HSPA9, FUS, pS6, YBX1	[6]
TMPRSS2-ERG Fusion	Genomic fusion (TMPRSS2::ERG)	TMPRSS2, ERG	[7]

Results

We identified DEG's 1314 tumor genes (Tumor versus Normal) ($\log_2FC \geq 1.5$ and $p_{adj} \leq 0.05$, see [Supplemental Table S1](#)). From these, Principal component analysis (PCA) plot shows good separation of tumor versus normal samples, with 15% and 12% variance explained by PC1 and PC2 (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. PCA plot of RNA-seq samples with DEGs for tumor and normal samples.

Among the DEG's, GRP (ERG $\log_2FC=2.66$, $p_{adj}=1.60e-17$) is the only gene among our putative biomarkers that is already used for prostate cancer diagnosis (see Table 1). In addition to DEGs, biomarkers whose fold change (FC) was ≥ 50 and average TPM of control samples ≤ 10 were identified as potential treatment targets (see Table 2).

Table 2 - Biomarkers whose fold change (FC) was ≥ 50 and average TPM of control samples ≤ 10 .

gene_name	foldChange	Avg normal	Std normal	Avg tumor	Std tumor
SCN1A	58.60	0.00	0.01	0.25	2.18
GC	53.93	0.06	0.15	3.21	20.61
ANKRD30A	107.03	0.01	0.04	1.58	7.72
OOSP2	51.12	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.22
FEZF2	89.64	0.01	0.02	0.54	4.78
CDC20B	52.09	0.12	0.26	6.15	74.30
DEFA5	1,959.56	0.10	0.24	189.00	2,480.52
DEFA6	932.12	0.06	0.13	55.49	693.42
SNORA73B	55.71	3.28	5.30	182.98	1,385.58
SNORA74A	132.91	0.22	0.42	29.16	243.45
RN7SKP9	63.39	0.03	0.08	2.04	15.88
SNORD17	137.17	1.86	2.23	255.81	2,368.35
SNORA74B	86.41	0.37	0.56	31.75	278.76
CCNJP2	64.18	0.00	0.01	0.18	1.39
AC004485.1	66.68	0.01	0.02	0.37	3.08
OR52Y1P	83.32	0.01	0.02	0.47	3.03
LINC00993	185.85	0.04	0.12	6.57	31.61
VN1R53P	69.26	0.00	0.03	0.34	1.71
TUSC7	66.01	0.00	0.01	0.16	1.19
Y_RNA	130.07	0.02	0.12	3.17	18.08

* foldChange = Tumor/Normal, Avg normal = Mean(Normal), Std normal = Std(Normal), Avg tumor = Mean (Tumor), Std tumor = Std(Normal)

Conclusions

From a bioinformatics perspective, the challenge of identifying biomarkers for cancer treatment seem to lie on the construction of cohorts. The important for treatment is to have information that can move the research forward. What can be done differentially expressed genes, depends on what the doctors in each hospital can work with.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This research used publicly available, non-identifiable, transcriptome of human data, already published on the GDC portal (<https://portal.gdc.cancer.gov/>) accessed on 2026-04-04.

Declaration of interest statement

The author declares he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Consent for publication

I hereby provide consent for the publication of the manuscript “Transcriptome analysis of prostate cancer”, including any accompanying images or data contained within the manuscript.

Availability of data and materials

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in GDC portal. A github with data and scripts to reproduce the results was made available at : https://github.com/datasciencebioinformatics/BiomarkerIdentification_ProstateCancer/

Authors' contributions

Felipe Leal Valentim (FLV) conceived and implemented the project

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FLV had the post-doc funded by FUSP but this work was performed independently.

References

[1] Hamed NW, Elbeljihy HS, Hussin SA, Fouda RM, Oy EK, W Magar R. From prostate specific antigen to genomic signatures: Advances in biomarkers for prostate cancer diagnosis and prognosis. *Transl Oncol.* 2026 Apr;66:102719. doi: 10.1016/j.tranon.2026.102719. Epub 2026 Feb 27. PMID: 41762538; PMCID: PMC12963913.

[2] Erho N, Crisan A, Vergara IA, Mitra AP, Ghadessi M, Buerki C, Bergstralh EJ, Kollmeyer T, Fink S, Haddad Z, Zimmermann B, Sierocinski T, Ballman KV, Triche TJ, Black PC, Karnes RJ, Klee G, Davicioni E, Jenkins RB. Discovery and validation of a prostate cancer genomic classifier that predicts early metastasis following radical prostatectomy. *PLoS One.* 2013 Jun 24;8(6):e66855. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0066855. PMID: 23826159; PMCID: PMC3691249.

[3] Knezevic D, Goddard AD, Natraj N, Cherbavaz DB, Clark-Langone KM, Snable J, Watson D, Falzarano SM, Magi-Galluzzi C, Klein EA, Quale C. Analytical validation of the Oncotype DX prostate cancer assay - a clinical RT-PCR assay optimized for prostate needle biopsies. *BMC Genomics.* 2013 Oct 8;14:690. doi: 10.1186/1471-2164-14-690. PMID: 24103217; PMCID: PMC4007703.

[4] Kuhl V, Clegg W, Meek S, Lenz L, Flake DD 2nd, Ronan T, Kornilov M, Horsch D, Scheer M, Farber D, Zalaznick H, Cussenot O, Compérat E, Cancel-Tassin G, Wild PJ, Chun FK, Mandel P, Moinfar F, Cohen T, Delee S, Kronenwett R, Doedt J. Development and validation of a cell cycle progression signature for decentralized testing of men with prostate cancer. *Biomark Med.* 2022 Apr;16(6):449-459. doi: 10.2217/bmm-2021-0479. Epub 2022 Mar 24. PMID: 35321552.

[5] Hamed NW, Elbeljihy HS, Hussin SA, Fouda RM, Oy EK, W Magar R. From prostate specific antigen to genomic signatures: Advances in biomarkers for prostate cancer diagnosis and prognosis. *Transl Oncol.* 2026 Apr;66:102719. doi:

10.1016/j.tranon.2026.102719. Epub 2026 Feb 27. PMID: 41762538; PMCID: PMC12963913.

[6] Roth JA, Ramsey SD, Carlson JJ. Cost-Effectiveness of a Biopsy-Based 8-Protein Prostate Cancer Prognostic Assay to Optimize Treatment Decision Making in Gleason 3 + 3 and 3 + 4 Early Stage Prostate Cancer. *Oncologist*. 2015 Dec;20(12):1355-64. doi: 10.1634/theoncologist.2015-0214. Epub 2015 Oct 19. PMID: 26482553; PMCID: PMC4679086.

[7] Hamed NW, Elbeljihy HS, Hussin SA, Fouda RM, Oy EK, W Magar R. From prostate specific antigen to genomic signatures: Advances in biomarkers for prostate cancer diagnosis and prognosis. *Transl Oncol*. 2026 Apr;66:102719. doi: 10.1016/j.tranon.2026.102719. Epub 2026 Feb 27. PMID: 41762538; PMCID: PMC12963913.

[8] Love MI, Huber W, Anders S. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biol*. 2014;15(12):550. doi: 10.1186/s13059-014-0550-8. PMID: 25516281; PMCID: PMC4302049.

